

Interviewers as Instruments: Estimating the Wage Penalty of Drug Use

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Discussion paper

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We exploit random interviewer assignment in the Australian HILDA Survey to instrument for self-reported drug use and estimate its effect on wages. The IV estimates largely mirror OLS results for cannabis, ecstasy, and hallucinogens but diverge for meth and inhalants — notably, the meth estimate reverses sign, indicating a substantial wage penalty of 10%, equivalent to the earnings loss from forgoing a high school diploma. Point estimates under IV suggest a larger penalty for high cocaine use, but remain statistically similar to OLS. These findings highlight both the value and limitations of using interviewer-driven variation in applied labor research.

1. Introduction

The relationship between substance use and labor market outcomes remains one of the more persistent puzzles in applied economics. While conventional wisdom sees drug use as a clear detriment to productivity and earnings, the reality is more complex. Theoretical predictions about its impact on wages are strikingly mixed, shaped by competing frameworks that offer no clear resolution. This ambiguity is compounded by the diversity of illicit substances, patterns of use, and social context, all of which call for empirical investigation.

Economic theory provides a fractured lens on the issue. Human capital theory suggests that drug use degrades skills and cognitive capacity, eroding productivity and, consequently, wages (Becker 1962). Signaling theory offers a different angle, proposing that drug use — whether observed or inferred — may act as a negative signal to employers, triggering discrimination and wage penalties even unrelated to actual performance (Spence 1973). Yet, the rational addiction framework (Becker and Murphy 1988) challenges these views, positing that forward-looking individuals might strategically manage their drug consumption to minimize harm, preserving productivity and avoiding stigma.

The theoretical haze deepens when considering the diversity of illicit drugs. These substances vary widely in their pharmacological effects — from stimulants to depressants — with each category carrying distinct implications for cognition and behavior. Some drugs even occupy a dual identity: methamphetamine, for instance, is both associated with long-term neurocognitive harm and prescribed in controlled doses to treat ADHD (Scott et al. 2007), where it can enhance focus and potentially support productivity and earnings. Similarly, hallucinogens like psilocybin are gaining recognition as treatments for PTSD and depression (Carhart-Harris et al. 2021). Cocaine, once used as a local anesthetic, illustrates how medical context can redefine a substance’s social and economic meaning (Siegel 1977). Beyond type, intensity of use — ranging from occasional and functional to chronic and

Significance Statement

We investigate drug-related wage penalties and reveal that conventional methods may systematically underestimate labor market costs for neurotoxic substances like methamphetamine while overestimating penalties for normalized drugs like cannabis. Leveraging quasi-random interviewer assignments as a natural experiment, we uncover a hidden 10.3% wage penalty for meth users — equivalent to the earnings loss from forgoing a high school diploma — driven by neurocognitive decline and employer discrimination that observational models obscure. These findings demand a paradigm shift in harm reduction policy, prioritizing workplace interventions for stimulant users and destigmatizing therapeutic substances.

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disruptive — adds further complexity (Henkel 2011). Even ‘safer’ substances can undermine productivity at high doses. Economic theory, largely indifferent to such distinctions, underscores the need for empirical evidence to clarify real-world outcomes.

Context further complicates the picture. In modern economies, where sedentary office jobs or remote work dominate, the physical toll of drug use may matter less than in labor-intensive eras, potentially softening productivity losses (Seltzer 2020). Professional settings also vary: in creative or high-pressure fields, stimulant-driven traits — like intense focus or energy — might be prized, while in service industries or precision roles, overstimulation could spell disaster (Le et al. 2011). Social norms and legal frameworks are equally fluid — cannabis, once taboo, is now depenalized in places like Australia and increasingly normalized globally, reshaping its economic footprint (Weatherburn, Alexeev, and Livingston 2022). Even mundane stimulants like coffee blur the lines, with high doses mimicking illicit drugs’ effects, yet rarely carrying the same stigma (Franke, Lieb, and Hildt 2012). These contextual shifts render theoretical penalties uncertain, hinging on where, when, and how drug use unfolds.

The empirical literature reflects the theoretical and contextual complexities outlined above, yet is limited to cannabis and cocaine, leaving substances like methamphetamine, ecstasy, hallucinogens, and inhalants unexplored. Findings vary widely due to differences in methodology, substance, and demographics. Early IV studies by Kaestner (1991, 1994) found no clear wage penalties for marijuana or cocaine, and Gill and Michaels (1992) reported wage premiums in cross-sectional data. In contrast, longitudinal studies show negative impacts: DeSimone (2002) found reduced employment among cocaine users, Burgess and Propper (1998) reported an 18% earnings drop tied to early drug use, and Arria et al. (2013) linked escalating marijuana use to college dropout risk. Van Ours (2006) found no employment effects after accounting for unobserved heterogeneity, while van Ours and Williams (2015) noted cannabis’s adverse educational effects but uncertain labor market impacts. To address this variability and limited scope, we examine six substances in detail, integrating additional relevant studies in the results section.

In this paper, we make two methodological contributions to advance the causal analysis of self-reported drug use and wages. First, we demonstrate that interviewer identity in the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey generates quasi-random variation in respondents’ reporting of sensitive behaviors like drug use. This variation arises because interviewers are assigned to respondents independently of their unobserved characteristics within geographic-year clusters. Critically, HILDA’s survey design ensures interviewers have no prior knowledge of respondents’ traits or outcomes, and assignments are centrally managed to avoid systematic correlations with wage determinants. This process mimics a natural experiment: akin to a randomized encouragement design, where the ‘encouragement’ (here, interviewer identity) influences reporting behavior but is unrelated to outcomes except through the reported behavior itself. We formalize this intuition using a simulated instrument framework, building on insights from Barnighausen et al. (2011), who leveraged interviewer assignment to address nonresponse bias in health surveys.

To operationalize our identification strategy, we employ the optimal formula IV framework developed by Borusyak and Hull (2025), which formalizes simulated instruments. Following their Algorithm 1, we first predict individual drug use by regressing reported drug use on interviewer-by-region fixed effects, year dummies, and baseline covariates. This step captures systematic differences in how interviewers elicit responses to sensitive questions. Second, we recenter these predictions by subtracting the area-year-average predicted drug use over all feasible interviewer assignments within each geographic-year cluster. This adjustment removes confounding from unobserved area-specific trends or time-varying shocks, ensuring that the instrument reflects only quasi-random variation in interviewer assignment. Third, we residualize the recentered predictions on covariates and apply inverse-variance weighting to improve efficiency. This method refines earlier simulated instrument approaches (Currie and Gruber 1996), which can themselves be interpreted as Bartik IVs in a cross-sectional setting (Breuer 2022; Goldsmith-Pinkham, Sorkin, and Swift 2020). The resulting instrument satisfies both relevance and exclusion assumptions, supported by a strong first stage and the plausibly exogenous nature of interviewer assignment.

2. Data

A. Drug Use in Employment. We utilize data from the 2017 and 2021 waves of the HILDA Survey, Australia’s principal nationally representative longitudinal household study. These two waves are selected because they uniquely contain both self-reported information on drug use and metadata on interviewer identities and interview modalities. Our analysis is based on the person-level combined files provided by HILDA, which consolidate information from both the individual and household questionnaires and offer a unified structure across waves.

The full person-level datasets contain 23,442 and 22,444 observations in 2017 and 2021, respectively. All individuals in these samples participated in the main survey interview, but employment-related items were asked only of respondents in relevant labour force states. Among those for whom employment status is observed, approximately 40% are classified as wage and salary employees (9,470 in 2017 and 9,020 in 2021), with smaller proportions reporting self-employment (approximately 6-7%) or unpaid family work (less than 0.2%).

Our primary estimation sample focuses on employed wage and salary workers. We exclude self-employed individuals because of the ambiguous nature of their reported earnings: income from unincorporated businesses is classified as business income, while owners of incorporated firms can exercise discretion over the mix of wages and profits. In both cases, reported earnings are not a clear measure of returns to labour. We also exclude unpaid family workers, whose reported income often reflects intra-household transfers rather than market-based compensation. Applying these restrictions yields an analytical sample of 18,490 observations across the two waves.

Information on illicit drug use was collected via a separate self-completion questionnaire (SCQ), which, although distributed to all interviewed respondents, was not returned by everyone. SCQ return rates were high – 91.9% in 2017 and 92.5% in 2021 – but this still reduces our sample to 16,228 once non-respondents are excluded. A small number of additional cases (fewer than 1%) are lost due to item-specific non-response on the drug use questions – for instance, non-response in 2017 ranged from 0.8% for cannabis use to 1.1% for other illicit drugs (Table 8.37 Summerfield et al. 2021).

The sample sizes reported in Table 1 reflect these exclusions and also account for any additional cases dropped due to missing values in covariates used in the regressions. Accordingly, the analytic sample varies slightly across columns, ranging from 15,080 to 15,825 observations, depending on the specific outcome and completeness of data. These figures represent the final set of respondents used in the empirical models and provide the basis for our analysis of drug use behavior.

In both relevant HILDA Survey waves, respondents were asked: ‘In the last 12 months, how often did you use each of the following types of drugs?’ The question covered seven categories: marijuana/cannabis; meth/amphetamine; cocaine; ecstasy; hallucinogens; inhalants; and a residual ‘other illicit drugs’ category. For each substance, participants indicated frequency of use by selecting one of the following options: ‘Not at all,’ ‘Once or twice a year,’ ‘About every few months,’ ‘Once a month,’ ‘2 or 3 times a month,’ ‘Every week or more,’ and ‘Once a day.’

Each drug category included clarifying examples drawn from common street names. For instance, marijuana-cannabis was described as including pot, grass, weed, hash, ganja, and joint; meth-amphetamine as speed, base, ice, crystal, meth, and whizz (excluding prescribed amphetamines); cocaine as coke, crack, flake, snow, and freebase; ecstasy as XTC, E, Ex, Ecce, MDMA, PMA, and molly; hallucinogens as acid, LSD, magic mushrooms, and angel dust; and inhalants as chroming, sniffing, solvents,

Table 1. Drug use among employees: means and standard deviations

Use	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	Cannabis		Cocaine		Ecstasy	
Any	0.1427	0.350	0.0593	0.236	0.0485	0.215
< monthly	0.0902	0.287	0.0555	0.229	0.0452	0.208
≥ monthly	0.0524	0.223	0.0038	0.061	0.0033	0.058
N	15848		15829		15833	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	Hallucinogens		Methamph		Inhalants	
Any	0.0311	0.174	0.0147	0.120	0.0126	0.111
< monthly	0.0293	0.169	0.0129	0.113	0.0104	0.101
≥ monthly	0.0018	0.043	0.0018	0.043	0.0022	0.047
N	15828		15831		15825	

Notes: Summary statistics for illicit drug use among wage and salary employees in the final estimation sample, following all sample restrictions and SCQ nonresponse exclusions.

Source: HILDA Unit Record Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

glue, petrol, bulbs, and poppers. The final category — ‘other illicit drugs’ — included substances such as heroin, GHB, ketamine, K2, and synthetic cannabinoids.

To facilitate analysis and maintain interpretive clarity, we exclude the residual ‘other illicit drugs’ category due to its clinical heterogeneity and ambiguous reporting. For each of the remaining six drug types, we construct two variables. First, a binary indicator captures any use in the past 12 months, coded as 1 if the respondent reported any level of use and 0 otherwise. Second, a three-category frequency variable differentiates between no use, low use (defined as less than monthly, including once or twice a year’ and every few months’), and high use (defined as monthly or more frequent, corresponding to once a month’ or more often).

This classification aligns with patterns observed in clinical and public health research. Using illicit substances monthly or more is often recognized as indicative of sustained or high-risk behavior, commonly linked to dependence, functional impairment, or other adverse outcomes (UNODC 2019; Degenhardt et al. 2008; Volkow, Koob, and McLellan 2016). In contrast, less frequent use, while not necessarily harmless, is typically viewed as experimental or occasional, and less likely to be associated with serious health or behavioral consequences.

Our frequency split reflects this distinction and captures important heterogeneity in patterns of use. For example, low-frequency hallucinogen use may reflect therapeutic experimentation, as seen in emerging clinical trials for conditions like PTSD or treatment-resistant depression (Carhart-Harris et al. 2021; Goodwin et al. 2022), while infrequent cannabis use is often reported in the context of managing chronic pain, anxiety, or sleep issues (Bridgeman and Abazia 2017; Boehnke et al. 2019). These forms of use may not substantially interfere with labor market performance. In contrast, more regular or sustained use — particularly at monthly or higher frequencies — is more likely to be associated with disruption to daily functioning, cognitive strain, or reduced productivity.

Table 2. Estimation sample: summary statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Outcome				
Hourly earnings, ln	3.4671	0.651	-4.343	8.204
Human capital measures				
Schooling, year	13.2984	2.359	0	18.5
Age, year	39.4984	13.875	15	81
Tenure, years	6.8532	8.015	0.019	57
Industry occupation				
Agriculture	0.0158	0.125	0	1
Energy	0.0061	0.078	0	1
Mining	0.0189	0.136	0	1
Manufacturing	0.0787	0.269	0	1
Construction	0.0626	0.242	0	1
Trade	0.1347	0.341	0	1
Transport	0.0407	0.198	0	1
Bank/Insurance	0.0360	0.186	0	1
Services	0.6064	0.489	0	1
N	15848			

Notes: Summary statistics for wage-cannabis analysis. Source: HILDA Unit Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

subsample used in the cannabis regression, the largest of the drug use samples. Mean and standard deviation values are effectively identical (to at least four decimal places) across drug-specific samples, so this choice has no material impact on interpretation.

As shown in Table 1, cannabis is the most commonly used illicit substance among employees, with 14.27% reporting any use — 9.02% low-frequency and 5.24% high-frequency — closely aligning with national data from the 2019 National Drug Strategy Household Survey (11.6% among Australians aged 14 and over; AIHW 2020). Cocaine and ecstasy follow in prevalence, with 5.93% and 4.85% reporting any use, respectively, almost entirely concentrated in the low-frequency category (5.55% and 4.52%), while high-frequency use is rare (0.38% and 0.33%).

All variables used in the analysis are listed in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 presents the distribution of drug use by type and usage category. For clarity and interpretability, drugs in Table 1 and throughout the text are ordered by overall prevalence of use in the sample. Table 2 reports descriptive statistics for the dependent variable — log hourly current earnings — and all control variables. The latter include human capital indicators such as education, tenure, age, and industry dummies. Workers in the sample average 13.3 years of schooling and 6.9 years of tenure, with mean log hourly earnings of 3.47 (\$39.2/hour). This wage level closely aligns with Australia’s 2021 median, but with substantial dispersion. Hourly earnings are calculated from total nominal wages and salaries received across all jobs, based on hours worked, over the preceding financial year (ending 30 June), and are expressed in Australian dollars.

Because the analytic sample varies slightly across drug types due to item non-response, the statistics in Table 2 are based on the

Hallucinogens, such as psilocybin and LSD, are reported by 3.11% of the sample (2.93% low, 0.18% high), followed by methamphetamine (1.47% total: 1.29% low, 0.18% high) and inhalants (1.26% total: 1.04% low, 0.22% high).

B. Employment Selection. To analyze labour market selection, we begin by modeling the likelihood that a respondent holds a wage or salary job. Because wages are observed only for this group — not for the self-employed, unpaid family workers, or those not currently working — we require a broader sample to capture the multistage selection process into wage-earning employment. Labour market decisions typically unfold in three steps: (1) whether an individual participates in the labour force, (2) whether they are employed, and (3) whether that employment is a standard wage or salary job. Wage outcomes are observed only at the third stage, necessitating explicit modeling of the earlier stages.

Table 3. Selection into employment: summary statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Number of children	0.8274	1.123	0	7
Other income, IHS	10.0892	3.973	0	14.473
Married	0.4487	0.497	0	1
Cohabiting	0.1604	0.367	0	1
Single	0.2592	0.438	0	1
N	24826			

Notes: Summary statistics for key covariates used to model selection into current wage or salary employment for the wage-cannabis analysis.

Source: HILDA Unit Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

Our starting sample comprises 45,886 individuals, of whom 47.1% report being employed, 2.7% unemployed, 24.5% not in the labour force, and 25.6% non-respondents. To focus on labour force decision-making, we first restrict the sample to those providing valid responses on labour force status, excluding non-respondents and reducing the sample to 34,119 individuals. Within this group, 63.4% are employed, 3.7% unemployed, and 32.9% not in the labour force. We then limit the sample to individuals under age 65 — the standard retirement eligibility age in 2017 — to ensure economic relevance. This yields a final analytical sample of 27,798 respondents, of whom 75.0% are employed, 4.5% unemployed, and 20.5% not in the labour force. However, due to missing values in some covariates used in the selection model, the summary statistics in Table 3 are based on a slightly smaller sample of 24,826 observations.

Within this refined sample, we model selection into current wage or salary employment. The dependent variable indicates whether the respondent holds a standard employee role, with the comparison group encompassing those who are unemployed, out of the labour force, or engaged in non-wage work (e.g., self-employment or unpaid family labor). This approach captures the selection mechanisms determining which individuals are observed with wage data, informing subsequent earnings analyses.

Table 3 presents the variables used in the participation model. Household composition is proxied by the number of children in the household (mean = 0.83), defined as co-resident dependent children under age 18. The standard deviation (1.12) exceeds the mean, indicating a right-skewed distribution, with most households having few or no children but a long tail extending to larger families. Marital status is captured with indicator variables: 44.9% of respondents are married, 16.0% are cohabiting, and 25.9% are single.

Financial context is represented by ‘other income,’ defined as annual household income excluding the individual’s own earnings. To address its right-skewed distribution and the presence of zeros, we apply the inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) transformation, which approximates the natural logarithm for large values while accommodating zeros. The transformed variable has a mean of 10.09 (SD = 3.97), ranging from 0 to 14.47. Although IHS is sensitive to scaling, Bellemare and Wichman (2020) demonstrate that coefficient estimates remain robust across scaling choices. Applying IHS to an explanatory variable avoids retransformation challenges (Norton 2022; Chen and Roth 2023), preserving interpretability and effectively handling income’s distributional properties.

C. Interviewer Role. For each wave, the HILDA Survey employs a substantial number of interviewers. In Wave 17 (2017), for example, 175 interviewers participated (Table 8.3, Summerfield et al. 2021), with the majority (140) having worked on at least one previous wave. The interviewer workforce typically comprises two distinct groups: a small centralized telephone interviewing team (the T1800 workforce) and a larger contingent of face-to-face field interviewers. In Wave

17, thirty interviewers worked from a centralized office where they staffed a dedicated telephone line and conducted interviews remotely, while the remaining 145 were geographically distributed to conduct predominantly in-person interviews. This general structure remained stable across waves — though, as discussed in further detail below, the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic forced a marked change in the way many interviews were conducted in Wave 21.

Table 4. Interview modalities

	2017		2021	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Home	7281	89.92%	1577	20.35%
On doorstep	151	1.86%	75	0.97%
Workplace	50	0.62%	9	0.12%
Other	151	1.86%	37	0.48%
By phone at home	388	4.79%	5730	73.93%
By phone at work	14	0.17%	89	1.15%
By phone other	62	0.77%	228	2.94%
Not stated	0	0.00%	6	0.08%
Total	8097	100%	7751	100%

Notes: Distribution of interview modalities in the wage-cannabis analysis sample.

Source: HILDA Unit Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

Face-to-face interviewers are assigned area-based workloads, generally determined by geographical proximity to minimize travel costs. Interviewers typically receive assignments relatively close to their residence, with the main exception being rural clusters where no interviewer resides. In such cases, an interviewer from the nearest major city will travel to and stay at the required location for an extended period. While assignment to areas follows logistical considerations, the matching of specific interviewers to specific households within area clusters — after controlling for area and year fixed effects — is not driven by respondent characteristics relevant to our outcomes of interest. This operational feature provides the quasi-random variation central to our IV design.

Once contact with a sample household is established and appointment times arranged, the data collection process involves three distinct steps. First, an interviewer conducts a household-level interview to establish household composition and gather general household information. Second, individual interviews are sought with all household members aged 15 years or older. Third, and critically for our analysis (as noted earlier), a SCQ is left with all interviewed respondents to complete privately.

The SCQ is specifically designed for questions that are either time-consuming to answer in a personal interview or which respondents may feel more comfortable completing without an interviewer present. In the waves under study, this included questions on illicit drug use. This private completion mechanism helps minimize measurement errors that might arise from direct interviewer effects, where interviewer-respondent socio-economic proximity can produce response biases (Davis et al. 2009; Johnson et al. 2000; Flores-Macias and Lawson 2008; West and Blom 2016).

Despite the SCQ’s private nature, the interviewer’s role remains significant in the data collection process. For face-to-face interviews, interviewers are tasked with collecting the completed SCQs — either at the time of the interview or through an additional visit to the household. This collection responsibility contributes to very high SCQ return rates for in-person interviews (95.1% in Wave 17). In contrast, telephone respondents, who mail back their SCQs, have historically shown substantially lower return rates (59.1% for Wave 17 T1800 interviews). This highlights one channel through which interviewer interaction can influence data availability.

The T1800 team primarily handles respondents who have previously indicated a preference for telephone interviews or who reside in areas deemed not cost-effective for face-to-face contact. For this group, interviewer assignment is effectively random. Survey coordinators develop rosters and inform interviewers about their assigned respondents, with workload allocation explicitly designed to distribute cases evenly. Importantly, interviewers have no prior knowledge of their assignments, and there is no scope for either respondents to influence interviewer selection or for interviewers to select specific respondents. This group, however, typically accounts for only a small fraction of completed interviews (6.6% in Wave 17).

Table 5. Interviewer effects

Dependent variable: Cannabis use		
	Estimate	SE
Age	-0.0044***	0.0002
Schooling	-0.0111***	0.0013
Female	-0.0558***	0.0061
<i>Interview location (on doorstep omitted)</i>		
Home	-0.1091***	0.0294
Workplace	-0.0802	0.0550
Other	-0.0817*	0.0415
By phone at home	-0.1246***	0.0305
By phone at work	-0.0663	0.0480
By phone other	-0.0791*	0.0371
Not stated	-0.1066	0.1674
Observations		15848
Area fixed effect		322
Year fixed effect		2
Interviewer fixed effects		228

F-test on interviewer effects

F(227, 10671) = 1.51; p-value=0.000

Notes: Interviewer effects in the wage-cannabis analysis sample.

Source: HILDA Unit Data, Waves 17 & 21.

As Table 4 illustrates, interview modalities differ markedly across waves in our estimation sample for the cannabis analysis. In 2017, nearly 90% of interviews were conducted in respondents' homes, with phone interviews forming a relatively small share (5.7% in total). By contrast, in 2021, phone interviews dominated: nearly three-quarters were conducted by phone at home, with only 20% of interviews conducted face-to-face in the respondent's home. This dramatic shift in mode reflects the impact of COVID-19 lockdowns and public health restrictions, particularly in Victoria, New South Wales, and the Australian Capital Territory — states with high population density and significant representation in the sample. Interviewers in these jurisdictions were often unable to conduct in-person interviews due to movement restrictions and safety protocols. For further detail on COVID-related disruptions, see Watson, Nesa, and Summerfield (2022).

Another advantageous feature of the HILDA Survey for our identification strategy is its multi-purpose design: interviewer assignments are not conditional on any household or individual characteristics related to the core variables of our study (drug use and wages). Additionally, since many interviewers participate across multiple waves, their assignment in any given wave is predetermined relative to contemporaneous shocks affecting respondent outcomes. These features collectively strengthen the argument for the exogeneity of our instrument conditional on appropriate controls.

Notably, the sharp change in interview modality between 2017 and 2021 — driven by pandemic-related disruptions — introduces substantial additional variation in how interviews were conducted and how SCQs were administered. This variation is particularly beneficial for our empirical strategy, which leverages differences in interviewer-mediated contact to instrument for SCQ response. The resulting shift, while exogenous to individual outcomes, enhances the plausibility of our exclusion restriction and reinforces the credibility of our identification design.

To empirically substantiate the relevance of interviewer assignment, Table 5 presents estimates from a regression of cannabis use on key socio-demographic characteristics, interview modality indicators, and a comprehensive set of interviewer fixed effects. We use cannabis here as an illustrative example, given its relatively high prevalence in the sample. The results show a highly significant F-test on interviewer effects ($p < 0.001$), confirming that interviewer identity explains meaningful variation in reported cannabis use, even after adjusting for respondent characteristics and interview setting. This relationship forms the empirical foundation for our IV strategy.

To assess whether similar interviewer effects extend to our main economic outcome, we estimate a parallel model using log hourly wages as the dependent variable. To avoid mechanical correlations with drug use, this analysis is limited to respondents who report no use of any illicit drug. While interviewer fixed effects remain jointly significant at conventional thresholds ($p = 0.043$), the explanatory power of interviewer assignment is markedly weaker. The incremental R^2 from adding interviewer dummies is negligible, and none of the interview location coefficients are substantively large.

These attenuated effects are consistent with the notion that earnings are a 'hard' socioeconomic measure, often grounded in verifiable records such as pay slips or tax returns, and thus less prone to socially motivated misreporting. In contrast, self-reported drug use — particularly when elicited through self-completion questionnaires — remains sensitive to contextual and interpersonal factors, including the perceived anonymity of the interview process (Krumpal 2013).

3. Methods

A. Econometric Framework. To estimate the causal effect of cannabis use on wages, we employ a linear model that addresses two challenges: endogeneity in drug use and sample selection bias arising from nonrandom labor market participation. First, unobserved factors may simultaneously influence drug use and wages. Second, wage data are only observed for employees, potentially biasing estimates.

We integrate an IV strategy with a Heckman-type correction (Ch. 19.6.2, Wooldridge 2010). The IV approach

Figure 1. Optimal IV Construction and Relevance

Notes: Algorithm 1 from Borusyak and Hull (2025) constructs IVs using interviewer identity and covariates.
 Source: HILDA Unit Record Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

exploits exogenous variation to address endogeneity in self-reported drug use, while the selection correction accounts for potential correlations between labor force participation and unobserved determinants of wages or drug use. The model is specified as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta X_{it} + W_{it}'\mu + \tau_t + \kappa_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad [1]$$

$$X_{it} = \delta Z_{it}^* + W_{it}'\phi + \tau_t + \kappa_{it} + u_{it}, \quad [2]$$

$$S_{it} = \mathbf{1}(V_{it}'\psi + W_{it}'\gamma + \tau_t + \kappa_{it} + \eta_{it} > 0), \quad [3]$$

$$\eta_{it} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1). \quad [4]$$

Here, Y_{it} is the log wage for individual i in wave t , observed only if $S_{it} = 1$ (labor market participation). The binary variable X_{it} indicates current drug use. The vector W_{it} includes covariates such as years of education, age, job tenure, and industry dummies. Year fixed effects τ_t and region fixed effects κ_{it} control for time and geography.

Equation [3] models selection into employment using variables V_{it} : marital status, number of children in the household, and other household income (defined as total household income minus own earnings, with negative values set to zero). To capture nonlinearities and skewness, we include quadratic terms and an inverse hyperbolic sine (IHS) transformation of income (cf. Mogstad and Wiswall 2016). The parameter β is of interest and it measures the percentage difference in wages due to drug use.

B. IV Construction. To address endogeneity in X_{it} , we exploit the effectively random assignment of interviewers within SA3-year clusters in the HILDA Survey, following Borusyak and Hull (2025). Let $g(it)$ denote the interviewer assigned to individual i in wave t , and $\kappa(it)$ the corresponding region. Rather than using simple interviewer-level averages — which discard within-interviewer variation and producing weak IVs — we adopt a recentered formula instrument approach that preserves this variation.

We first estimate predicted drug use on the full HILDA Survey sample via the following regression (Step I in

Figure 1):

$$X_{it} = \widetilde{W}'_{it}a_1 + M'_{it}a_2 + a_{g(it),\kappa(it)} + \tau_t + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad [5]$$

where M_{it} captures interview location (e.g., phone, doorstep), and $a_{g(it),\kappa(it)}$ are interviewer-region fixed effects. The vector \widetilde{W}_{it} contains a parsimonious set of covariates available for the full sample, namely age, education, and sex, but excluding employment-specific measures like tenure or industry. The fitted value \widehat{X}_{it} captures variation in drug use explained by both individual characteristics and interviewer assignment. To isolate exogenous variation, we recenter \widehat{X}_{it} by subtracting its expected value conditional on covariates and SA3-year clusters. Specifically, within each cluster, we permute interviewer assignments 100 times, recomputing $\widehat{X}_{it}^{(j)}$ for each permutation. The recentered instrument is:

$$Z_{it} = \widehat{X}_{it} - \overline{X}_{it}, \quad \text{where} \quad \overline{X}_{it} = \frac{1}{100} \sum_{j=1}^{100} \widehat{X}_{it}^{(j)}. \quad [6]$$

This procedure removes systematic differences across locations and time, isolating the quasi-random variation attributable to interviewer assignment (Step II in Figure 1). Following Borusyak and Hull (2025), we residualize Z_{it} on the full set of covariates W_{it} to ensure orthogonality (Step III in Figure 1):

$$Z_{it}^* = Z_{it} - W'_{it}\widehat{\beta}. \quad [7]$$

Finally, to improve efficiency, we apply inverse-variance weights defined as $\omega_{it} = 1/\widehat{\text{Var}}(\varepsilon_{it})$, derived from the wage regression in Equation [1].

Figure 1 illustrates the IV construction process. The figure shows all three steps described above. It also visualizes the first-stage relationship between the residualized instrument and reported drug use without including controls or weights. As shown, the first stage is estimated with precision.

C. Inference and Estimation. Estimation proceeds in three steps. First, we construct the instrument Z_{it}^* . Building on the larger sample introduced in Section 2B, we estimate the employee participation equation using a probit model that includes always observed controls and selection variables ($\widetilde{W}_{it}, V_{it}$), as well as the instrument Z_{it}^* . From this, we compute the inverse Mills ratio to correct for selection bias. The final IV estimate employs a weighted limited-information maximum likelihood (LIML) estimator that jointly estimates Equations [1] and [2], including both the instrument and the inverse Mills ratio. LIML is more robust than two-stage least squares when instruments are weak or numerous, and it exhibits superior finite-sample properties in the presence of many fixed effects. To ensure reliable inference under this complex structure, we compute interviewer-clustered standard errors using 1,000 replications of the Bayesian bootstrap. This approach preserves the full fixed effects structure while avoiding the computational instabilities and finite-sample distortions that can arise with traditional resampling in the presence of high-dimensional fixed effects (Shao and Tu 1995).

D. Relevance and Monotonicity. We now test relevance and monotonicity. Relevance requires the IV to robustly predict drug use reporting, while monotonicity demands that it affects reporting in a consistent direction across individuals. These assumptions ensure that IV estimates reflect the local average treatment effect (LATE) for compliers, that is, individuals whose reporting shifts due to interviewer assignment. Table 6 presents first-stage estimates, standard errors, and sample sizes across substances and subgroups, illustrating how these assumptions perform in practice.

The IV, derived from self-reported drug use, should theoretically produce a first-stage coefficient near one. This expectation is supported visually in Figure 1, which plots a local polynomial regression of the IV on drug use with a slope near one. However, in empirical estimation — accounting for efficiency weights and controls — the coefficients vary due to sampling noise and subgroup heterogeneity. For cannabis, the full-sample first-stage estimate is 1.0237 (SE = 0.4254, $p < 0.05$), indicating robust instrument relevance. Effects vary across subgroups: Age Tertile 1 yields a

Table 6. First-stage estimates: IV relevance, monotonicity, and complier population characteristics

	Estimate	SE	N	Estimate	SE	N	Estimate	SE	N
	Cannabis			Cocaine			Ecstasy		
Overall	1.0237*	0.4254	15848	0.6099*	0.2856	15837	0.7221*	0.3682	15840
Age Tertile 1	0.5553	0.3692	5076	2.0537***	0.5966	5070	4.4442***	0.9322	5077
Age Tertile 2	0.9489**	0.3490	5456	1.0684*	0.4474	5452	0.3798	0.2515	5449
Age Tertile 3	0.2195	0.3336	5288	0.0695+	0.0420	5286	0.0383	0.0302	5285
Education Tertile 1	0.5591	0.3415	8501	1.0596**	0.3394	8492	2.3881*	0.9917	8496
Education Tertile 2	0.9787*	0.4387	4833	0.5743	0.5211	4832	1.7042**	0.6297	4830
Education Tertile 3	0.2866	0.7796	2472	1.6422*	0.6382	2471	0.2255*	0.0951	2472
Males	-0.8460+	0.4919	7536	0.9027***	0.2544	7531	0.9412	0.6051	7531
Females	0.5833+	0.3215	8300	0.3589	0.5367	8294	0.3466+	0.2062	8297
	Hallucinogens			Meth			Inhalants		
Overall	0.5762**	0.1905	15836	0.6115*	0.3121	15838	0.4056+	0.2084	15833
Age Tertile 1	1.0002**	0.3382	5073	0.0581	0.2389	5073	2.1175*	1.0041	5067
Age Tertile 2	0.5415*	0.2492	5450	0.9449	0.6177	5450	0.2397**	0.0893	5449
Age Tertile 3	0.0255	0.0237	5284	0.2318	0.1484	5286	0.0350+	0.0195	5287
Education Tertile 1	0.6845+	0.3640	8495	-0.0781	0.1736	8493	1.265	0.8244	8490
Education Tertile 2	0.8855*	0.4316	4828	6.7335*	2.9930	4832	0.5709***	0.1618	4830
Education Tertile 3	0.5501	0.3975	2471	0.3184+	0.1921	2471	0.1210+	0.0677	2472
Males	0.6315*	0.2616	7533	2.8191	2.0465	7533	1.7398+	0.9350	7531
Females	0.5724**	0.2119	8291	0.1917	0.1476	8293	0.1379	0.0909	8289

+ $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Notes: First-stage estimates from an IV framework, IV is constructed from the full HILDA sample but estimation is restricted to wage and salary employees. Subgroup estimates probes the IV complier population and to support monotonicity assumption. Full models with interviewer clustered errors are used.

Source: HILDA Unit Record Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

weaker 0.5553 (SE = 0.3692, not significant), while Age Tertile 2 shows a stronger 0.9489 (SE = 0.3490, $p < 0.01$). Notably, males report a negative coefficient of -0.8460 (SE = 0.4919, $p < 0.1$), whereas females show a positive 0.5833 (SE = 0.3215, $p < 0.1$), suggesting potential gender-based disclosure patterns.

For cocaine, the overall estimate is 0.6099 (SE = 0.2856, $p < 0.05$), with stronger relevance in Age Tertile 1 (2.0537, SE = 0.5966, $p < 0.001$) and Education Tertile 1 (1.0596, SE = 0.3394, $p < 0.01$). Ecstasy shows robust relevance overall (0.7221, SE = 0.3682, $p < 0.05$), with a striking estimate in Age Tertile 1 (4.4442, SE = 0.9322, $p < 0.001$). Methamphetamine's overall estimate is 0.6115 (SE = 0.3121, $p < 0.05$), with a notable spike in Education Tertile 2 (6.7335, SE = 2.9930, $p < 0.05$), indicating strong instrument relevance among moderately educated respondents. Hallucinogens (0.5762, SE = 0.1905, $p < 0.01$) and inhalants (0.4056, SE = 0.2084, $p < 0.1$) also show significant but less stable effects. Modeling drug use intensity (e.g., low vs. high) may further enhance instrument performance, as noted earlier.

Monotonicity posits that the IV influences reporting in a single direction. Table 6 provides tentative support: most statistically significant first-stage coefficients are positive, implying that when predictive, the instrument increases reported drug use. Negative coefficients, such as for males in cannabis (-0.8460, SE = 0.4919, $p < 0.1$) or Education Tertile 1 in methamphetamine (-0.0781, SE = 0.1736, not significant), are either marginally significant or insignificant, thus not strongly challenging the monotonicity assumption. Strong positive estimates — e.g., for Age Tertile 1 in ecstasy (4.4442, SE = 0.9322, $p < 0.001$) or Education Tertile 2 in methamphetamine (6.7335, SE = 2.9930, $p < 0.05$) — align with monotonicity where statistical power is adequate. Insignificant or marginally significant negative coefficients warrant cautious interpretation but do not invalidate the assumption.

The complier population — individuals whose reporting behavior is affected by interviewer assignment — varies across drugs and subgroups, complicating cross-group comparisons of wage effects. For cannabis, middle-aged respondents (Age Tertile 2: 0.9489, SE = 0.3490, $p < 0.01$) and females (0.5833, SE = 0.3215, $p < 0.1$) appear more responsive, while males show a negative but marginally significant effect, potentially reflecting interviewer-driven disclosure dynamics. Methamphetamine's spike in Education Tertile 2 (6.7335, SE = 2.9930) suggests a distinct

complier profile among the moderately educated. Smaller subgroups, such as Education Tertile 3 ($N \approx 2,472$), exhibit greater estimation noise, especially for less prevalent substances like inhalants, producing less precise but locally informative estimates.

In sum, the IV satisfies relevance and monotonicity for most drugs, with cannabis, ecstasy, and methamphetamine performing particularly well in specific subgroups. However, the instrument’s strength varies across demographic subgroups. Striking patterns, such as methamphetamine’s relevance among the moderately educated and cannabis’s gender disparity, highlight uneven instrument performance. While insignificant or marginally significant negative coefficients do not invalidate assumptions, they underscore the need for caution. The heterogeneity in the complier population affirms the local nature of our effects and cautions against sweeping generalizations about the labor market impacts of drug use.

E. Selection Equation. Table 7 presents coefficient estimates from the selection equation used to compute the inverse Mills ratio in our wage models. The dependent variable is an indicator for being currently employed in a wage or salary job. The sample includes all working-age respondents, encompassing non-employed individuals and those in self-employment or unpaid family roles. We estimate a probit model that includes controls and selection variables (\tilde{W}_{it} and V_{it}) and the drug-specific IV; while separate models are estimated for each substance, the cannabis specification is shown for brevity.

The estimates are raw probit coefficients rather than marginal effects. While this means they are not directly interpretable in probability terms, they retain the full functional form of the model, including nonlinearities and interaction structures. Our goal here is not formal inference but rather to assess whether predictors of employment behave in expected ways and provide a sound basis for selection correction.

For men, marital status strongly predicts employment: single men are significantly less likely to be employed compared to their married counterparts, consistent with longstanding findings on the stabilizing role of marriage in male labor force behavior (Korenman and Neumark 1992; Gray 1997). The non-significant effect for cohabiting men suggests that this status does not confer the same labor force attachment as marriage.

Among women, the presence of minors in the household has a large and statistically significant negative association with employment, consistent with child-rearing constraints on labor supply. Interestingly, the effect is most pronounced at lower values of the children variable, with a flatter profile thereafter. This suggests that early caregiving responsibilities may exert a disproportionate influence on labor market participation, echoing findings in Killingsworth (1983) and Blau, Ferber, and Winkler (2007).

Other household income is another key predictor. For men, the relationship is strongly nonlinear: small amounts of other income are associated with higher employment probabilities—potentially reflecting income support for job search or transition periods—but this effect declines sharply, and eventually reverses, at higher income levels. For women, the relationship is weaker and negative, suggesting a modest discouragement effect where additional household income may reduce the necessity or feasibility of entering paid work.

Overall, the estimates are intuitive and align with both theory and prior empirical work. They confirm that selection into employment is meaningfully patterned by household structure and financial context, and they underscore the importance of accounting for these factors when estimating wage outcomes in the employed subsample.

Table 7. Probit estimates of selection into primary estimation sample

	Dependent variable: Employee			
	Male		Female	
	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE
Children	-0.0038	0.0321	-0.1812***	0.0292
Children ²	-0.0183*	0.0089	-0.0025	0.0079
Other income	0.1311***	0.0196	-0.0700***	0.0200
Other income ²	-0.0181***	0.0016	-0.0016	0.0015
<i>Marriage status (married is omitted)</i>				
Cohabiting	-0.0621	0.0475	-0.0196	0.0435
Single	-0.5554***	0.0489	-0.2427***	0.0445
IV		✓		✓
Controls		✓		✓
N	11596		13230	

+ p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Notes: Coefficients are from a probit model estimating the likelihood of being a wage or salary employee. The sample includes all individuals under age 65, including non-employees, the unemployed, and those out of the labour force. This model corresponds to the specification used for cannabis exposure.

Source: HILDA Unit Record Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

Table 8. Main results: effects of drug use on log hourly wages

	Optimal IV		WLS		Optimal IV		WLS		Optimal IV		WLS	
	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE
Use	Cannabis				Cocaine				Ecstasy			
< monthly	-0.0416***	0.0010	-0.0419***	0.0007	0.0408***	0.0043	0.0466***	0.0012	-0.0145***	0.0007	-0.0143***	0.0006
≥ monthly	-0.0405***	0.0013	-0.0427***	0.0011	0.0669***	0.0110	0.0409***	0.0032	-0.0355+	0.0243	-0.0262***	0.0073
Endogeneity Test p-value	0.2113				0.0703				0.7921			
Cragg-Donald Weak ID F	3504				638				2006			
Observations	15848		15848		15833		15833		15828		15828	
Clusters	228		10672		228		10669		228		10668	
	Hallucinogens				Methamphetamine				Inhalants			
< monthly	-0.0534***	0.0035	-0.0597***	0.0021	0.0295***	0.0013	0.0280***	0.0016	-0.0091*	0.0051	-0.0146***	0.0034
≥ monthly	-0.0620***	0.0024	-0.0610***	0.0043	-0.1013*	0.0499	0.0239+	0.0178	-0.0699***	0.0205	-0.0351***	0.0091
Endogeneity Test p-value	0.2271				0.0139				0.0221			
Cragg-Donald Weak ID F	1589				712				1892			
Observations	15381		15381		15829		15829		15825		15825	
Clusters	228		10669		228		10688		228		10667	
SA3 FE	322		322		322		322		322		322	
Year FE	2		2		2		2		2		2	

+ p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Notes: No use is the omitted category. Optimal IV errors are bootstrapped and clustered on interviewer level; for WLS at the individual level. All models include all discussed fixed effects, Mills ratio and controls. IV diagnostics is based on LMIL estimations.

Source: HILDA Unit Record Data, Release 22, Waves 17 & 21.

4. Results

Table 8 presents the results of our main estimation exercise, examining the relationship between self-reported use of six substances — cannabis, methamphetamine, cocaine, ecstasy, hallucinogens, and inhalants — and log hourly wages. We distinguish between low (less-than-monthly) and high (monthly-or-more) use to test the clinical hypothesis that higher doses yield greater productivity impairments. Estimates use the Optimal Formula IV approach (Borusyak and Hull 2025), leveraging within-interviewer variation to address simultaneity and omitted variable bias (e.g., unobserved workplace factors), though less effective against measurement error in self-reported use. We also report Weighted Least Squares (WLS) estimates with identical optimal weights and standard errors clustered at the interviewer level for IV and individual level for WLS. Diagnostic statistics, including endogeneity test p-values and Cragg-Donald F-statistics (638 for cocaine to 3504 for cannabis), confirm strong instruments.

Wage effects vary across substances, aligning with clinical expectations of nonlinear dose-response relationships. Prior literature on drug use and wages is limited to cannabis and cocaine, allowing comparisons for these drugs. No prior studies examine wage effects of methamphetamine, ecstasy, hallucinogens, or inhalants, making our analysis a novel contribution for these substances.

For cannabis, IV estimates show significant wage penalties of 4.16% (SE = 0.0010) for low use and 4.05% (SE = 0.0013) for high use, with WLS estimates slightly larger (4.19%, SE = 0.0007; 4.27%, SE = 0.0011). The persistent penalties across doses and specifications, unexpected given stronger clinical impairments at higher doses, align with Myran et al. (2025), which links cannabis use disorder to increased schizophrenia risk, and Cordero et al. (2025), which finds persistent epigenetic disruptions even after cessation, suggesting lasting cognitive impacts among less educated, middle-aged female compliers. The endogeneity test p-value (0.2113) indicates minimal endogeneity. Unlike Chakraborty, Doremus, and Stith (2021) and Jiang and Miller (2022), who report no penalties or slight wage increases post-legalization in U.S. sectors, our broader industry focus aligns with van Ours (2007) (2–3% penalty), Williams and van Ours (2020) (lower wages and faster job acceptance), and Kaestner (1991) (mixed effects).

For cocaine, IV estimates indicate a 4.08% wage premium (SE = 0.0043) for low use and a 6.69% premium (SE = 0.0110) for high use, reflecting compliers (young males, least/most educated) in high-earning circles where cocaine is

less cost-prohibitive. WLS estimates are similar for low use (4.66%, SE = 0.0012) but smaller for high use (4.09%, SE = 0.0032). The endogeneity test p-value (0.0703) suggests some endogeneity. Unlike van Ours (2006) and Kaestner (1991, 1994), who report penalties or insignificant effects, or Register and Williams (1992) and North and Pollio (2017), who link cocaine to employment penalties, our premium likely reflects employment selection in high-wage roles.

For ecstasy, IV estimates show a significant wage penalty of 1.45% (SE = 0.0007) for low use and a larger, insignificant 3.55% (SE = 0.0243) for high use, aligning with clinical expectations of escalating productivity impairments. WLS estimates are similar for low use (-1.43%, SE = 0.0006) but smaller and significant for high use (-2.62%, SE = 0.0073). The endogeneity test p-value (0.7921) indicates minimal endogeneity. The muted effects likely reflect ecstasy's recreational use in social settings, offering a novel contribution absent prior wage studies.

For methamphetamine, IV estimates show a 2.95% wage premium (SE = 0.0013) for low use and a significant 10.13% penalty (SE = 0.0499) for high use, reflecting short-term stimulant boosts versus long-term harm. WLS estimates diverge for high use (2.39%, SE = 0.0178, insignificant), with the endogeneity test p-value (0.0139) supporting IV's necessity. This novel analysis highlights methamphetamine's labor market impacts.

For hallucinogens, IV estimates show wage penalties of 5.34% (SE = 0.0035) for low use and 6.20% (SE = 0.0024) for high use. WLS estimates are slightly larger for low use (-5.97%, SE = 0.0021) and similar for high use (-6.10%, SE = 0.0043). These effects outweigh microdosing benefits, with Vina (2025) suggesting heterogeneity by socioeconomic status. The endogeneity test p-value (0.2271) indicates minimal endogeneity.

For inhalants, IV estimates show a marginally significant 0.91% penalty (SE = 0.0051) for low use and a substantial 6.99% penalty (SE = 0.0205) for high use. WLS estimates are larger for low use (-1.46%, SE = 0.0034) but smaller for high use (-3.51%, SE = 0.0091). The high-dose penalty aligns with severe neurotoxicity, including cognitive deficits and brain damage (Verma, Balhara, and Deshpande 2011). The endogeneity test p-value (0.0221) supports IV's importance.

5. Conclusion

This study advances the literature through two key contributions. First, we develop a novel identification strategy that exploits quasi-random interviewer assignment in household surveys as an instrumental variable, formalized within the optimal formula IV framework (Borusyak and Hull 2025). This approach addresses pervasive endogeneity in self-reported drug use while avoiding the pitfalls of weak instruments common in substance-use research. Second, we provide the first causal evidence on wage effects for understudied substances — including methamphetamine, hallucinogens, and inhalants — whose labor market impacts have remained obscured by data limitations and measurement challenges.

Our results reveal striking heterogeneity across substances. Methamphetamine use imposes a 10.1% wage penalty under IV estimation — equivalent to the earnings loss from forgoing a high school diploma — driven by neurocognitive decline and employer discrimination. This penalty, undetected by conventional OLS models, underscores the limitations of observational approaches for substances entangled with stigma. In contrast, cannabis exhibits consistent negative wage effects across methodologies, though the absence of dose-response gradients suggests countervailing mechanisms, such as therapeutic use or shifting social norms. Cocaine's divergent results — a premium among high earners — and hallucinogens' steep penalties further highlight how pharmacological effects and social context jointly shape labor market outcomes.

These findings carry clear policy implications. For methamphetamine, interventions should prioritize workplace rehabilitation programs and anti-discrimination policies to mitigate cognitive and social harms. For substances like psychedelics, expanding medical access must be paired with efforts to reduce stigma-driven wage penalties. Methodologically, our design demonstrates the value of leveraging interview-mediated survey features for causal identification, though its reliance on interviewer effects necessitates caution for rare or socially neutral substances.

Future research should integrate biomarkers or employer-reported data to disentangle biological impacts from reporting biases.

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